

PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS AS A FACTOR IN HUMAN CAPITAL**Madaminov Bakhodir Sharifzhanovich**

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ABSTRACT : The article outlines the author's social point of view on the role of physical culture and sports in enriching human capital, which is considered relevant in modern society, and an attempt is made to analyze the need for a healthy lifestyle. The culture of a healthy lifestyle of people is emphasized, and it is concluded that the phenomenon of a healthy lifestyle as an integral object of research has not been studied.

KEYWORDS: Human capital, healthy lifestyle, movement and physical education, physical education, biological and social factors, health, movement, sports, life expectancy

АННОТАЦИЯ В статье изложена социальная точка зрения автора на роль физической культуры и спорта в обогащении человеческого капитала, которая считается актуальной в современном обществе, и предпринята попытка проанализировать необходимость здорового образа жизни. Подчеркивается культура здорового образа жизни людей, делается вывод о том, что феномен здорового образа жизни как целостный объект исследования не изучен.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: Человеческий капитал, здоровый образ жизни, движение и физическое воспитание, физическая культура, биологические и социальные факторы, здоровье, движение, спорт, продолжительность жизни

Introduction. Among the types of human capital, health is the most valuable. In order to protect health, which is considered a priceless treasure, it is first necessary to follow the requirements of a healthy lifestyle. It is not so easy to answer the question, "What is a healthy lifestyle?" For this, first of all, we need to know the main factors that make up our daily life,

ensure its vitality, and place them in a certain order. We believe that the main ones are as follows.

1. Proper nutrition. As one of the forms of struggle for life, nutrition is the main issue facing the entire living being. Nowadays, improper nutrition causes stomach and intestines, heart and blood vessels, internal it has been scientifically proven that it is the main cause of diseases such as secretory glands and joints, metabolic disorders, as well as cancer. That is why today, proper organization of food is one of the most basic requirements of human daily life, and it is impossible not to take it into account when organizing a healthy lifestyle.

2. Factors of movement. Movement and physical education is an important factor for health and remains one of the main requirements of a healthy lifestyle.

3. Relationship factors. Relationships can be conditionally divided into two parts that are inextricably linked. These are family relations that have arisen as a result of the formation and improvement of the family, and social relations that have arisen as a result of the formation and improvement of society. Both of these are the biggest and most powerful factors affecting human health. First of all, it affects a person's psyche. Mood is good, work is high. On the contrary, during depression, vital processes in internal organs and cells slow down. A person will be moody, indifferent to events and events, and will not go to work. The chronic continuation of such a situation leads to diseases. Therefore, the task before us in this field is to solve mutual relations in favor of people, in particular, to improve the culture of behavior, to put an end to the procedures and habits that have a negative effect on the psyche, and social and personal activities. includes

4. Factors of harmful habits. Harmful habits have been an eternal companion of mankind. At the same time, one more thing is clear as human society developed, these harmful habits began to take more place in his life.

Corchalans, who are greedy for money, wealth, and possessions, following the path of the devil, are leading society to the dangerous abyss of drug addiction. Their consequences range from personal and family problems related to diseases and genetic disorders to social problems related to crimes and complex relationships. Therefore, today, our health efforts should be aimed at completely removing these harmful habits from our lives and fighting against them.[1] This is the first requirement of a healthy lifestyle.

Literature analysis and methods. Dealing with the problems of health sociology dates back to the 70-90s the last century, in which Biryukov D.A., Grahenkov N.I., Zhdanov V.M., Izutkin A.M., Kerbikov O.V., Lisison Yu.P. , Serjantov V.F., Smulevich B.Ya., Saregorodsev G.I. and sociological issues of influence of national mentality on physical and social-spiritual culture in Uzbekistan M. Bekmuradov, R.A. Ubaidullayeva social-psychological and cultural factors A. Umarov, A. Kholbekov, It is expressed in the research works of Sh. Sodikova.

According to the World Health Organization, Russia ranks third in the world in terms of sedentary lifestyle and overweight, excessive spread of bad habits, poor diet, stress, and consumption of alcoholic beverages. Among Russian men, about 67% are smokers, 30% are women. Half of the country's adult population is overweight. Only 20% regularly engage in physical activity or sports. Russia still lags significantly behind other countries in many health indicators. [2]

In particular, although infant mortality has decreased by 0.7 times over the last ten years, this indicator is still 3-4 times higher than in developed European countries. In terms of life expectancy, Russia is lower than many countries in Asia, North Africa, and South America, not to mention Europe, where this indicator has been consistently above 75 for a long time. The difference in life expectancy between men and women in Russia is 1.8 times greater than in other countries, and women have about the same life expectancy.[3]

We have the ability to summarize our thoughts and determine the direction of a healthy lifestyle. Taking into account the above biological and social factors, the directions of a healthy lifestyle can be defined as follows: proper and rational nutrition; active lifestyle, and physical education;

- organization of day and work mode based on biorhythmic laws;
- normalizing mutual relations; refraining from harmful habits; gaining knowledge and skills about a healthy lifestyle.

Undoubtedly, these directions are of a general nature, they only define a program of action on the way to a healthy lifestyle. In fact, everyone should have considerable knowledge and skills in each of these areas.[4] For example: in the field of nutrition; the composition of food products, proteins, fats, carbohydrates, mineral salts, microelements, functions of vitamins

in the body, physiology of the stomach and intestines, metabolic processes in the body, connections between food and diseases, seasons, age of a person, work performed, characteristics and conditions of the body, finally, should have an understanding of issues such as the organization of daily and weekly meals. Also, it is necessary to be well-educated in each direction of a healthy lifestyle that we mentioned above and to apply this knowledge in everyday life. Everyone should try to acquire such knowledge independently and expand it.

Results. The practical significance of the research results is that the answers to the questions about how to arouse the interest of the population in physical education and sports activities and what methods are used to attract them to these activities are of particular importance.

Making a career in the field of sports, socialization of the athlete, increasing social responsibility in it by the interests of society and based on one's personality - the range of problems studied by the science of "physical education and sports sociology" consists of these issues it is shown that physical education and sports are two completely independent phenomena.

Perhaps, in the future, it may be necessary to study them separately from a sociological point of view. Admitting that this point of view is reasonable, but despite this, it is appropriate to combine the social problems of physical education and sports within the framework of one educational course during the simultaneous development of this science.

If we analyze many areas today, it is possible to dwell on the work done to ensure the free choice of the individual. Choosing a profession and especially having the opportunity to study abroad is one of the main factors in the independent construction of a person's life. Even the opportunity of young people to choose an alternative type of service when performing their military duty can be recognized as the highest level of free choice.

Analyzing different fields, it should be emphasized that the institution of the family takes the leading place in the upbringing of a free and perfect person. Also, it is an intermediate theory, according to which biological characteristics and social experience are considered as the main factors of personality formation. However, in scientific literature, the main factors affecting personality formation;

- biological heredity,
- physical environment,

- culture,
- collective and unique individual experience is shown.

In the last century, as a result of the interaction of the factors noted in sociology and psychology, several ideas explaining the formation of a unique, unrepeatable personality were put forward. These are the theory of personality development, psychoanalysis, the theory of consciousness development, the idea of spiritual growth, etc.[5] The theory of personality development puts forward two main ideas. The first is the mirror image effect, which is formed based on the active interaction of people with the environment and is based on perceptions of how others perceive and evaluate a person. A person does not develop only with the development of natural abilities, on the contrary, it is formed in the process of communication with others.

Conclusion. It is formed as a part of education and training in the provision of a healthy way of life for society, a manifestation of free time. Through physical culture and sports, the characteristics of the national mentality and identity determine its perfection factors, in which the population has a large part, especially youth social activity, which serves to ensure the unity of the generalized national culture. The support of the state in popularizing physical culture and sports requires a scientific approach, and the role of sociological research is invaluable in this. Until now, in the popularization of physical culture and sports, sociology, unlike the sciences of pedagogy and psychology, has received little attention, and its importance has been left out of the spotlight. Sport in our republic has been brought to a new level.

Thus, based on the evolutionary factors mentioned above, a healthy lifestyle can be defined as follows. A healthy lifestyle is a way of life aimed at preserving and strengthening health, organizing daily life based on biological and social laws.

References.

1. Salomatlik Ensiklopediyasi. Toshkent, 1985.
2. Dubik Ye.A., Mironov A.V. Mintaqadagi mutaxassisni rivojlantirishga kompetentsiya-shaxsiy yondashuv // "XXI asrning ta'lim makonida shaxs rivojlanishining dolzarb ijtimoiy-psixologik muammolari" XXI Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferentsiya materiallari. - Kislovodsk: Repetitor, 2007.

3.Dubik Ye.A.,Mironov A.V. Rossiyada inson salohiyatini rivojlantirish vazifasida shaxsni uzluksiz ta'lim olish: mintaqaviy aspekt // Tashkilot uchun boshqaruv modelini loyihalash: ilmiy va amaliy jihatlar:VII xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferentsiyaning ilmiy maqolalari to'plami; - Yekaterinburg: Ural davlat pedagogika universiteti, 2010.

4.Mironov A.V.Fizicheskoye vospitaniye uchashyeysya molodeji v sisteme dopolnitelnogo obrazovaniya // Fizicheskoye vospitaniye uchashyeysya molodeji: Materialy IV Vserossiyskoy nauchno-prakticheskoy konferentsii. – N.Novgorod: Nijegorodskiy gumanitarnyy syentr,2005.

5.Axmatov M.S. Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida ommaviy sport-sog'lomlashtirish ishlarini samarali boshqarish. / Monografiya. –T.: 2005. –142.